

Article

Women's Empowerment in India: Looking Beyond Electoral Politics

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Political Process, Women's Participation, Political Participation, Representation, Discourse on Empowerment, Global Situation regarding women's participation

Abstract

This paper tries to explore the possibilities of looking into the future of the participative democracy from a substantial political output process rather merely normative process. Though there is considerable space for action oriented programmes for enhancing women's political participation & representation in our country, it is not being reflected in action, rather than only in rhetoric. Though the increasing demand for reservations and the subsequent constitutional provision might provide some impact on the larger space provided to our women folk, beyond household, which might be political as well as apolitical and it will have an impact on reservation for seats for them. However the existing scenario of political participation of women is not encouraging. Comparing to the situation at the

global level, it is giving very sad picture. Though in terms of human development indicators, the situation is not encouraging, simultaneous political picture is also equally bad. In this context, the author tries to explore the possible reasons for those conditions as well as looking forward for a possible future course of action to overcome this. Statistics were obtained from international databases, in particular those of the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) and the United Nations Development Programme.

Introduction

The Constitution of India is based on the principles of equality and guarantees equality before law and equal protection to all its citizens. It not only guarantees fundamental rights and freedoms, but also prohibits discrimination on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, and place of birth. However, these rights have remained only in paper and have not been turned into practice in reality. As such, women have been denied social, economic, civil and political rights in many spheres. An important area where women have been inadequately represented is in the political sphere. Articles 325 and 326 of the Constitution of India guarantees political equality, equal right to participation in political activities and right to vote respectively. While the latter has been accessed, exercised and enjoyed by a large number of women, the former i.e., right to equal political participation is still a distant dream. Lack of space for participation in political bodies has not only resulted in their presence in meager numbers in these decision making bodies but also in the neglect of their issues and experiences in policy making.

The government of India, noting the low participation of women in politics; acknowledging the recommendations of the Committee for Status of Women Report, 1974; and drawing from the pioneering experience of Karnataka which provided reservation for women in its three tier Panchayat Raj system (institutions of local self governance) in the year 1983; adopted an

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affirmative action for providing reservation for women in these institutions in the year 1993. The 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act introduced not less than 33 per cent reservation for women in the Panchayati Raj Institutions in the rural areas. Similarly, the 73rd & 74th Constitutional Amendment Act introduced similar reservation for women in Nagar Palika and Municipalities in towns and urban areas. With these Constitutional Amendments, over three million women are now actively participating in shaping the policies and programs of the country, though only at the local levels of governance. However, such affirmative action is lacking at the higher echelons of governance at the State and Central levels. Prior to the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments, only the State of Karnataka had reservation for women in institutions of local self-governance.

A brief review of the literature

Among the activists and social scientists who have studied women empowerment are Bari (Bari, 2005) Bora & Dube (Bora, 1999,) Chaturvedi (.Chaturvedi, 1999) (Chowdhary, 24 September 2007.) , Duverger (Duverger, 1955), Garg (Garg, 2007), and Madhok (Madhok, 1995).

Analysis of Women in Parliament – A Global Perspective

The trend in terms of women's representation over the past decade has been a slow process. In 1975, at the time of the First World Conference on Women in Mexico City, women accounted for 10.9 per cent of MPs worldwide. Ten years later, in 1985, women's representation had increased by only 1 percentage point, to an average 12 per cent. In 1995, the number of women had actually decreased to 11.6 per cent but a new impetus for women's participation in decision-making found expression at the Fourth World Conference on Women, held in Beijing in 1995, and the adoption of the Beijing Platform for Action (BPFA). By 2000, the number of women in Parliaments had increased to 13.4 per cent of parliamentarians in the lower houses of

Parliament. In October 2005, a new global high was reached, as 16.2 per cent of the members of lower or single houses of parliament were women, and 14.8 per cent in upper houses, bringing an overall total average of 16.0 per cent in all parliaments. While steady, the progress has been slow. If current incremental rates continue, it will not be until 2025 that an average of 30 per cent will be reached, and not until 2040 that parity will be achieved. They continue to be in a minority in National Parliament. As per figures compiled recently by the IPU, women constitute only 7.1 per cent of the total MPs (as on 30/4/2007). Data region wise shows a large variation with almost equal participation of women and men in NordiCountries (41.7 per cent) to just 8.8 per cent in the Arab states. In the other parts of the world, the proportion of women MPs is more or less the same, varying between 15 to 20 per cent.

Table. 1. Global Perspective of Women in Parliament 1945-2005.

	1945	1955	1965	1975	1985	1995	2000	2005
Number of parliaments	26	61	94	115	136	176	177	187
% women representatives (lower house or unicameral)	3.0	7.5	8.1	10.9	12.0	11.6	13.4	16.2
% women representatives (upper house)	2.2	7.7	9.3	10.5	12.7	9.4	10.7	14.8

Source: IPU, 2005. Women in Politics: 1945-2005.
<http://www.ipu.org/english/surveys>.

Indian Scenario

In Indian politics women continue to be an 'extinct species'. At least that's what the agendas of all major political parties in the country reveals. The first phase of Lok Sabha elections were on April 16 and women candidates were barely to be found on the contestants' lists. Even principal parties like the congress and the BJP, despite their vociferous commitment to 33 per cent reservation for women in Parliament and state legislature, have not dared to field many from the fair sex for forthcoming elections. That's one area where the two parties seem to agree notwithstanding their otherwise bitter political differences. In all the elections held since independence, women had the voting rights. The percentage of seats won against the seats contested is showing a declining trend only because the number of women contesting elections has increased sharply. However, it may be seen that voting by women in all tiers of government has always been a feature of the Indian Polity since 1947. Due to the paternalistic family and male dominated political structures which do not provide space for women in decision making bodies, women constituted 3.1% of the total contestants in 1996 election and did not occupy more than 6.10% of the total seats in the state legislative assemblies and Parliament. The number of women contestants in Parliamentary elections has not increased significantly over the years. Political parties are still reluctant to field women candidates at national level. In the early days of the Indian republic, the number of women representatives was a mere 22, which was a lowly 4.4% of the total seats in the LS. The sixth LS in the year 1977 saw an all time of just 19 women representatives. The twelfth LS had 44 women i.e. 8.8% of the total.

Participation of Women in the Parliament
– Lok Sabha (Lower House) and Rajya Sabha

(Upper House) Women are poorly represented at higher leadership levels. Even historically, it is observed that women's participation in positions of power in both houses of the Parliament has never exceeded 15 per cent of all seats. Table below presents the participation of women in the two houses of the Parliament.

Table: 2. Participation of Women in the Rajya Sabha

Year	No. of Seats	No. of Women	No. of Women %
1990	245	24	9.8
1994	245	38	15.5
1996	245	20	8.2
1997	245	19	7.8
1998	245	19	7.8
1999	245	20	8.2
2000	245	22	9.0
2001	245	22	9.0
2002	245	25	
2003	245	25	10.2
2004	245	28	11.4
2009	245	26	10.7

Source: Rajya Sabha Secretariat.

In the Rajya Sabha, their proportion remains constant at about 8 percent of the total seats. The exception has been the 1994 elections wherein their representation was at 15.5 percent. The Table shows that there is increase in the Representation of women after 2000, the trend after has been rising but a little fall in 2009 elections.

Table.3. Increase in the Share of Women Members of Parliament

	1996	1998	1999	2004 2009
Total Constituencies	543	543	543	543 543
Total No. of women candidates	491	274	284	355 445
Total No. of women winners	40	43	49	45 60

Source: Gender Statistical Report 2006-07.

Table. 4. State-wise No. of Women Candidates in Elections in 2004.

State/Union Territory	No. of Women Candidates	No. of Women who Won
Andhra Pradesh	21	3
Arunachal Pradesh	0	0
Assam	6	0
Bihar	14	3
Goa	1	0
Gujarat	11	1
Haryana	8	1
Himachal Pradesh	2	1
Jammu & Kashmir	4	1
Karnataka	10	2
Kerala	15	2
Madhya Pradesh	30	2
Maharashtra	29	5
Manipur	1	0
Meghalaya	0	0
Mizoram	0	0
Nagaland	0	0
Orissa	9	2
Punjab	10	2
Rajasthan	17	2
Sikkim	0	0
Tamil Nadu	23	4
Tripura	0	0

Uttar Pradesh	61	7
West Bengal	34	4
Chhattisgarh	12	1
Jharkhand	13	1
Uttaranchal	5	0
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	1	0
Chandigarh	1	0
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	1	0
Daman & Diu	0	0
National Capital Territory Of Delhi	15	1
Lakshadweep	0	0
Total (All India)	355	45

Source: www.eci.nic.in.

While there is the increased participation in grass root political movements; it is not getting translated into a growing share of women in the formal political structure of the country. Amongst the several reasons for such a situation is the growing money power and muscle power required to contest even the smallest of elections in India, the intimidation, violence and slander that a women candidate has to face combined with the traditional male domination that seeks to keep her indoors. Narrow electoral arithmetic and the necessity of fielding a winning candidate makes most political parties shy away from fielding more than a token number of women candidates. And if they are fielded at all, kinship and affinity factors play a major role. It is very common to observe that the relatives of politician are promoted and supported to emerge as politicians. Increasingly, women have stood for elections and got elected as members of State Legislative Assemblies and the Parliament. Some studies of Parliamentary participation indicate that women members participate more actively in 'women's issues' – health, welfare, atrocities against women, crimes like dowry and violations of human rights. This participation is confined to the more articulate women.

Table-5: Male-Female Representation in Selected State Assemblies

State	Latest year's for which data is available	Total	Male	Female	Percent of Female

Andhra Pradesh	1999	294	266	28	9.52
Arunachal Pradesh	1999	60	59	1	1.67
Assam	1996	122	116	6	4.92
Bihar	2000	70	61	19	5.86
Delhi	1998	70	61	9	12.86
Goa, Daman & DIU	1999	40	38	2	5.00
Gujarat	1998	182	178	4	2.20
Haryana	2000	90	86	4	4.44
Himachal Pradesh	1998	68	62	6	8.82
Jammu & Kashmir	1996	87	85	2	2.30
Karnataka	1999	224	218	6	2.68
Kerala	1996	140	127	13	9.29
Madhya Pradesh	1998	320	294	26	8.13
Maharashtra	1999	288	276	12	4.17
Manipur	2000	60	59	1	1.67
Meghalaya	1998	60	57	3	5.00
Mizoram	1998	40	40	0	0.00
Nagaland	1998	60	60	0	0.00

Orissa	2000	147	134	13	8.84
Pondicherry	1996	30	29	1	3.33
Punjab	1997	117	110	7	5.98
Rajasthan	1998	200	186	14	7.00
Sikkim	1999	32	31	1	3.13
Tamilnadu	1996	234	225	9	3.85
Tripura	1998	60	58	2	3.33
Uttar Pradesh	1996	424	404	20	4.72
West Bengal	1996	294	274	20	6.80
Andhra Pradesh	1999	294	266	28	9.52
Arunachal Pradesh	1999	60	59	1	1.67
Assam	1996	122	116	6	4.92

Source: Election Commission of India's Website (www.eci.gov.in).

Women's political representation at the state level as gauged by their membership in state legislatures is abysmally low. The latest data from the States show that Delhi (12.86 per cent) has the highest proportion of women members followed by Andhra Pradesh (9.52 percent) and Kerala (9.29 per cent). Other States with relatively high proportions of women in the State Assemblies include Orissa (8.84

per cent), Himachal Pradesh (8.82 per cent) and Madhya Pradesh (8.13 per cent). It is clear from the above analysis that women's participation in the state legislatures is even lower than their participation in the Parliament and the reasons for the variation needs to be analyzed further. What is clear however that in the given situation as represented above, it is necessary to facilitate and create a conducive atmosphere for women to participate in various levels of political activities. In that background, the 85th Amendment Bill seeking

one-third reservation for women in the parliamentary and legislative seats becomes an extremely important, particularly for the political participation of women.

Impact of Women's Low Political Participation

Historically women are marginalized in decision making and leadership by a variety of processes, in various parts of the world. In most societies, women lack experience of decision making and leadership in the public arena because girls, in contrast to boys are advised to be submissive and not to be active in various political practices of the governance system due to socio-cultural practices. In most traditional societies girls are kept largely within the confines of the household and family where they are protected and taught to accept the decisions that others parents, teachers or brothers make on their behalf. As a result of this lack of experience in a public context, girls tend to lack self-confidence and skills needed to function effectively in positions of formal leadership. An added handicap for many is their lack of capacity due to discrimination in access to education and training: in most countries, women have higher levels of illiteracy and fewer years of schooling than men. The Beijing Platform for Action for women across the globe also identifies several specific issues that need to be addressed, including socialization and negative stereotyping, which have kept decision making the primarily the domain of men. The Platform calls to create a gender balance in governance and administration; integrate women into political parties; recognize that shared work and parental responsibilities promote women's increased participation in public life; promote gender balance within the UN system; work toward equality between women and men in the private sector; establish equal access of women to education, increase women's capacity to participate in decision-making and leadership; and increase women's

participation in the electoral process and political activities.

Institutional cultures that are unfriendly to women are not usually the result of deliberate policies but the consequences of their development over a period of time to meet the needs and situations of men, who have for so long dominated the public domain and who have different needs, priorities and concerns from women. Men need to become aware of the ways in which their assumptions, attitudes and behavior are gendered to reflect their own situation, exclude a woman's perspective and thus obstruct women's equal participation. Women and men together must then negotiate a new institutional setting that provides space for both groups in each and every sphere of life, society as well as governance system.

As a matter of fact status of women cannot be improved unless women are adequately represented in decision making bodies. The Committee on the Status of Women in India in its report Towards Equality (1974) recommended 30 per cent reservation for women in decision making bodies." The government has acknowledged the need to increase the number of women in decision-making processes at all levels, as early as in 1976. As a first step to facilitate women's participation in politics, in 1993, it introduced 33 percent reservation for women in institutions of local governance through the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments. It has also provided one-third reservation for women to the posts of Presidents and Vice Presidents in these institutions. While the government has succeeded in facilitating women's participation by providing for reservation at the lower levels of governance, it has failed to do so in passing the reservation Bill for women in the higher echelons of political institutions i.e., in the State Assemblies and the Parliament.

Conclusion

The prevailing political environment of our country which reflects corruption, criminalization and communalization discourages women from entering politics. It was observed that with the entry of women in the Panchayati Raj Institutions, as a result of the reservation policy for women, the overall atmosphere has visibly changed. There has been a considerable reduction in the incidence of corruption, due to the pressure exerted by them on their male colleagues in creating transparency and accountability in governance system. As a result of which the overall use of money and muscle power and criminalization of politics has reduced to certain extent. There has been an increase in the incidence of violence against women elected representatives and those in positions of power. This has been more as resistance to their entry into politics and a backlash against particularly articulate and politically active women. Violence is used as a means to subdue and silence them. This reveals that the entry of women into political institutions have changed the atmosphere more positively and has made it more transparent and accountable. If affirmative action has a positive influence on the environment at the PRI level, it is all the more reason that the same would happen at the higher levels of governance. The 33% reservation for women has been interpreted in such a manner that it restricts the scope for women to contest the elections in general constituencies to certain extent. It is interpreted by male members of the political parties that women can contest only against the 'reserved constituencies'. This implies that the 'general' seats are exclusively meant for men. This deprives women of opportunities to contest against the general category despite having the potential and aspiration to do so. The lack of vibrant and supportive constituencies has adversely affected women's participation in governance. Where the constituency is aware and informed, they are able to influence and change the quality of governance as

well as the reflection of the voice of the women in general. Hence it is of extremely important to look into the matter of 1/3rd representation of women at all level of political bodies, starting from panchayat to parliament and the bill should be passed with massive support and be implemented in letter & spirit.

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